

Chat

Secretaries Difier and 15 others were evited to the meeting.

Thursday

Tuinkamer and Alexanderzaal left the chat.

Tuinkamer and Alexanderzaal were invited to the meeting.

Tuinkamer and Alexanderzaal left the chat.

Today

08:33 Meeting ended: 29s

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08:51 Ellen Peeters started recording to the cloud

Executive Report: Responsible Academic Assessment at TU/e

90% project completion, November 2025
Dr Andrea Kis & Julma Braat

RRCe

RESPONSIBLE
RESEARCH
COMMUNITY
EINDHOVEN

Recognizing and Rewarding Responsible Academic Practices at TU/e

Dr. Andrea Kis & Julma Braat

90% project completion – 21/11/2025 – Please note the **disclaimer** on the final page

As Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) continues to grow and evolve in line with its Strategy 2030, talent attraction, assessment, and retention remain at the heart of our success. To align performance management practices with our aspirations and values, we secured funding within the national Recognition and Rewards program for this project. This report on **Responsible Academic Assessment** outlines evaluations of our current assessment practices and recommendations for evidence-based improvements.

The findings of this report expand on previously known risks and provide deeper evidence of **inefficient use of resources, and vulnerabilities** that may impede the university's long-term ability to attract and retain talent, advance academic excellence, and remain competitive.

A **holistic quality assurance framework** is recommended as the most effective lever for resolving root causes and supporting sustainable strategic development. The second recommendation covers a **holistic approach to performance management (PM)** to strengthen talent development and retention. Thirdly, **community collaboration** is recommended to strengthen TU/e's position as an (inter)national leader in academic culture.

Why Responsible Academic Assessment?

External trends

- 1. (Inter)national developments:* Sector-wide agreements, such as DORA, Recognition & Rewards, and CoARA, mark the growing consensus on academic assessment systems needing to embody the goals and principles of responsible research assessment. Commitment to these guidelines can only be achieved by redesigning career paths, performance management, and (academic) leadership to incorporate evidence-based facilitators for innovation, responsibility, and impact.
- 2. Competing for excellence:* Intensifying competition on the academic talent market, combined with limited resources in higher education, challenges in talent attraction, and shifting societal expectations about workplace norms, exacerbate difficulties in attracting, developing, and retaining talent. Competitiveness and sustained growth are increasingly reliant on human resource management infrastructures and capabilities.
- 3. Leaders of tomorrow:* Markers of long-term academic excellence are also changing as academic leaders increasingly recognize the relevance of research integrity, institutional fairness, academic citizenship, and more broadly, responsible academic practices. A value-driven approach aligned with organizational missions and values can position universities as forerunners, facilitating technology leadership through societal impact and institutional credibility.

Internal discussions

1. *Personal, seamless, and connected*: Ongoing agreements (Institutional Plan, People Strategy) underscore our commitment to support all tasks with affordable, scalable, and user-friendly facilities. At the intersection of academic and operations activities, performance management is a high-priority area to achieve our goals in talent attraction, development and retention. Yet a lack of dedicated resources (data for quality assurance, expertise scarcity, integrated operations) and a weak connection between academic needs and professional products and services lead to inefficiencies and suboptimal circumstances.

2. *One TU/e*: Our move towards a strong and inclusive community with shared goals is aligned with international best practices and our ambitions. However, the practicalities of finding a balance between community and the individual, building bridges, breaking down silos, and opening channels that connect professional and academic communication have yet to be achieved. Trust and engagement are reliant on commitment paired with system thinking.

3. *Success depends on dialogue*: Embodied by community engagement connected to e.g. interdepartmental knowledge sharing in the IFCs (2017), the EYAE (2018), piloting the Biographical Sketch (2024), the creation of our CORE values (2024), the development of Everybody Professor (2024), and the Institutional Plan (2025). We already exemplify the strength in community engagement. To become international frontrunners and further embody our CORE values, we need to design our view on performance management in co-creation with the community.

Translating needs into action

These external and internal trends converge in a need to improve the most critical and under-addressed barriers of institutional change: **assessment practices**, in which strategy becomes decision. With external funding, we started tackling these challenges to **pilot modern, evidence-based performance management practices**.

The project

To examine the current state of assessment practices, this project used a mixed-methods research approach. Through collaborations between professional and academic staff members*, we examined current assessment procedures, identified problem areas and risks, **designed the bases for short-term solutions and long-term recommendations**, and started fostering community engagement to aid further development.

The design of our short-term solutions focused on the **training for BAC members ‘Responsible Academic Assessment – from principles to practice’**, encompassing multiple levels of change (cognitive, affective, normative, and behavioral), the kick-off of the **Responsible Research Community Eindhoven (RRC/e)** on September 18th, 2025 with active involvement from LIS, META/e, Sustainability Office, OSC/e and HRM, and the development of a **database of best practices**.

Our results reconfirm previously identified risks – such as inefficient use of resources (financial, human, and time). Compared to earlier inquiries, we reveal broader, more detailed sets of concerns connected to legal compliance exposures, estimated financial and social safety impacts, and long-term reputational risks at the (inter)national level. We identify and provide deeper qualitative evidence (N = 191 observational points) on six main areas of concerns:

1. BAC procedures: unclear roles, responsibilities, and expectations reduce decision quality, increase workload, and undermine consistency.
2. Handling transgressions: gaps in addressing conflicts of interest, integrity issues, and unsafe dynamics erode social safety and perceived fairness.
3. Recognition & Rewards: persistent, traditional research-centric norms limit recognition of diverse profiles and open science contributions, and constrain non-traditional career paths.
4. Interview and assessment skills: lacking interview skills, insufficient preparation, structure, and time management lead to suboptimal hiring outcomes and legal-reputational risks.
5. Self-management: sustained time pressure, emotional load, and procedural frustrations contribute to rushed decisions and erosion of institutional values.
6. Equity, Diversity & Inclusion: limited awareness of bias and inclusive practices restrict diversity, reduces innovation capacity, and undermines equal opportunity.

These factors collectively pose a threat to our capacity for excellence, (financial) sustainability, and competitiveness. These categories and observational points have informed the design of the training Responsible Research Assessment as well as the policy recommendations in this report.

Figure 1. Risks associated with academic assessment-related concerns, by categories

Strategic recommendations

In line with research findings, as well as external drivers and internal values and aspirations, we have outlined the following main recommendations for TU/e:

Quality assurance

While targeted solutions could be developed for each individual problem, the primary recommendation is to adopt a **holistic, solution-oriented approach** that addresses the underlying systemic issues rather than isolated symptoms. The most critical and recurring root cause is the **absence of standardized quality assurance (QA) mechanisms** across key hiring, promotion, and academic management processes. Without clear quality assurance standards, the identified challenges are likely to persist and intensify with growth.

Addressing this core issue provides a foundation that will attract talent, strengthening our strategic ambitions by improving academic circumstances and opportunities.

Failure to do so may result in increasing operational inefficiencies, delayed realization of our strategic key-enabling objectives for talent, and in some domains, the inability to achieve desired outcomes altogether.

Table 1. Discussion topics: QA recommendations, by level of institutional impact

	Fair	Good	Excellent
Actions	Support ✓ training for BACs ✓ scalable training for HR ✓ other interventions	Assign QA manager to design processes: ✓ develop and align quality assurance metrics with needs	Use an innovative approach to quality assurance ✓ data-driven ✓ proactive
	Incorporate existing expertise ✓ BAC secretaries ✓ IFC members ✓ senior policy advisors	✓ standardize post-process evaluation ✓ continuous improvement cycle (PDCA)	
	Implement digital facilities ✓ AI for reporting ✓ harmonization (unified processes and forms)	✓ risk management	
Win	Problem fix (liability... etc) Upscaling expertise to provide a basis for quality assurance	Relieve academic leaders and reduce risk	Contribution to goals on talent attraction, development and retention

Performance management

While TU/e has been working toward more robust processes for the annual dialogue, BACs and academic assessment, a **holistic approach to performance management (PM)** is necessary to ensure talent development and retention. Although several processes and instruments are available, there is a **lack of alignment between individual and collective levels** resulting in unclear development pathways for individual academics and a lack of strategic approach to talent development. Without clear alignment of performance management tools, the benefits of diversity in career profiles at the team level will not become apparent.

Aligning the different phases in talent identification and talent development provides the foundation for developing talent in line with the strategic needs of TU/e. Failure to do so does not only lead to inefficiencies in performance management process but may also result in a negative impact on talent retention. Embedding performance management into InSite will result in increased efficiency and proper transferal of institutional memory, transparency and data-driven decision quality.

Table 2. Discussion topics: PM recommendations, by level of institutional impact

	Fair	Good	Excellent
Actions	Align BACs with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ R&R profiles and criteria ✓ annual dialogue ✓ quality indicators (e.g., teaching, research, valorization supervision, leadership, collegiality, team skills, social safety, OS and other expertise) Reduce resource needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ extend use of Biographical Sketch to R-BAC (reduce application materials) Increase efficiency, reduce frustration for candidates and BAC members alike: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ transparent, privacy-compliant setup ✓ uniform and transparent process 	Automation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ embed whole process in InSite ✓ collect data -> QA Reduce resource needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ extend use of Biographical Sketch to annual dialogue (create alignment) Increase efficiency, reduce frustration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ function-specific onboarding (career development, performance management) 	Reduce resource needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ number of senior academics involved ✓ time spent on preparation and reporting (automation, aligned processes) Increase efficiency, reduce frustration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ align all performance management processes
Win	Regular dialogue on development, less frustration and time spent on the process	Enabling strategic workforce planning More time for reputation increasing academic activities (research, education, impact)	No need for M-BACs and F-BACs as embedded in performance cycle 25% estimated cost savings (1000K€ in 5 years)

IMAGE A: IDEAL STATE

CAREER DEVELOPMENT

HORIZONTAL (broadening profile)

VERTICAL (promotion)

PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

STRATEGIC WORKFORCE PLANNING, PROCEDURAL ALIGNMENT, QUALITY ASSURANCE

IMAGE B: CURRENT STATE

CAREER DEVELOPMENT

VERTICAL (promotion)

Community collaboration

Community collaboration in **the Responsible Research Community Eindhoven (RRC/e)** is crucial to advance the discussion on overlapping concepts, principles and communities. While many TU/e members are already engaging in responsible academic activities, there is a **lack of alignment between initiatives**, resulting in isolated pockets advancing responsible research, academic citizenship, and interdisciplinary collaboration. Connecting community members already working on topics, such as Open Science, Recognition & Rewards, social safety, research integrity, sustainability, and talent development, and encouraging others to engage will **strengthen TU/e's position as a national and international leader** in academic culture.

Performance management and talent development need to match the needs of our community. To be accepted by and embedded in practice, it needs to be developed in collaboration with the academic community. RRC/e encompasses both academic and professional staff and can become a breeding ground and accelerator for new developments to enable our objectives in talent development and retention.

Table 3. Discussion topics: collaboration recommendations, by level of institutional impact

	Fair	Good	Excellent
Actions	Connecting silos within the community through aligned topics (responsible academic activities) ✓ manage the RRC/e ✓ organize annual event	Starting a dialogue about assessment ✓ centralized vs decentralized policy and QA ✓ One TU/e, one assessment ✓ academic and professional profiles	Strengthening infrastructures for teamwork by supporting culture (incentives, responsible leadership, and collaborative competencies and skills) ✓ system (technology, policy) ✓ structure (team science, enabling diverse career paths)
Win	Enabling One TU/e Aligning professional and academic staff, building bridges between academic and service departments	Enabling One TU/e Creating robust agreements about basics to support robust decision-making processes	Attractive employer Increasing talent development and retention Focus on team collaboration, increasing collegiality, and decreasing power dynamics

Contributors

Project members: Andrea Kis (project lead), Julma Braat (project management), Lisa Idebolo, Kristina Korshunova

Responsible Research Community members: Open Science Community Eindhoven, Eindhoven Meta-Science Center, Library and Information Services, HRM Policy Team, Sustainability Office TU/e, Research Support Office, Integrity and Social Safety Desk, Communication Expertise Center, other members and collaborators

Research participants and advisors: IFC members and secretaries, BAC members and candidates, supervisors and managers, HR advisors and talent attraction team members

Other contributions: Klara Strecker, Jolien Strous, HRM colleagues

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Disclaimer

The strategic recommendations included in this document are intended as input for dialogue and co-creation. Their purpose is to support informed decision-making regarding responsible academic assessment at TU/e. They should not be interpreted as a predefined action list or as decisions to be implemented.

This document represents an initial, executive-level summary. A more extensive version - detailing the underlying research, project outputs, and micro-level recommendations - will be circulated in December.